

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Amino Acids in Dioxane + Water Mixtures at 298 K

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The dissociation constants of a number of amino acids have been determined pH-metrically in dioxane + water mixtures at 298 K. The free energies of transfer [$\Delta G_i^\circ(1)$ and $\Delta G_i^\circ(2)$] for the reactions, $\text{RH}_2^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{RH}^\pm + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ (1) and $\text{RH}^\pm + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{R}^- + \text{H}_3\text{O}^+$ (2) have been coupled with the free energies of transfer for neutral amino acids [$\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{RH}^\pm)$] and H^+ ions ($\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{H}^+)$) to get the free energies of transfer of RH_2^+ ($\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{RH}_2^+)$) and R^- ($\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{R}^-)$) from water to mixed solvents. $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{RH}_2^+)$ and $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{R}^-)$ are negative and positive respectively. These give the quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions of the cations and anions of the amino-acids. The results have been discussed in terms of structural changes of the mixtures resulting in the change of acid-base properties and solute-solvent interactions. Attempts have been made to determine the interaction energies of the ions using the scaled particle theory.

Solvents have important effects on the physicochemical properties of weak acids and bases. The solvent effects are particularly important for biomolecules and proteins in view of their changed structure and properties in these solvents. The amino acids form the basic units of proteins; it may be useful to study the solvent effects on the dissociation and solvation process of the amino acids. With these objects in view, the effects of mono-ol + water (like methanol + water, ethanol + water, isopropanol + water and t-butanol + water mixtures) and diol + H_2O (like ethylene glycol + water) mixtures on the dissociation constants of amino acids have been studied extensively in our laboratory¹⁻³. But all these solvents studied are hydrogen-bonded solvents. It is desirable to extend our studies in aprotic solvent systems like dioxane. The selection of dioxane stems out from the fact that it is a non-hydrogen bonded cyclic ether, miscible with water in all proportions and boiling point (101.3°) of which is close to that of water. Moreover, the dipole moment is close to zero (0.45 D) and the dielectric constant (or relative permittivity) is 2.2. Thus, the study of the dissociation constants of amino acids in dioxane + water mixtures would enable us to understand the effects of wide variation of dielectric constants and solvent characteristics on the solvation, dissociation, specific solute-solvent interactions and other structural factors associated with these processes. The studies are of particular importance in view of the zwitterionic nature of the amino acids and their importance in living systems. These considerations led us to study the dissociation constants of the amino acids (glycine, α -alanine, β -alanine, L-valine, L-proline, L-leucine, L-methionine, L-glutamine, L-asparagine, L-threonine and L-phenylalanine) in dioxane + water mixtures.

Results and Discussion

The acidic and basic dissociation equilibria and the dissociation constants of the amino acids can be represented by equations,

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} a_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{a_{\text{RH}_2^+}} = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{C_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \times \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (3)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{a_{\text{H}^+} a_{\text{R}^-}}{a_{\text{RH}^\pm}} = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{R}^-}}{C_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \times \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (4)$$

The activity coefficient data of the different ionic forms of the amino acids in aqueous and mixed solvents are not available in literature. In these experiments, addition of neutral electrolytes was avoided as these are likely to form molecular combinations⁴ which may be pronounced in D + H_2O mixtures of low dielectric constant. In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change due to (i) salt effect (f_i) and (ii) medium effect⁵ (f_m). So the use of neutral electrolyte is carefully avoided as the strong ion-ion interactions of unknown magnitude are likely to mask the 'medium effects' for the reactions^{2,3}.

The complications arising from the addition of excess neutral electrolytes in the determination of pK values had been discussed earlier in details⁶. We, therefore, prefer to work with dilute solutions so that the activity coefficients (for all ionic species including H^+ ion) may be regarded to be unity and medium effects can be determined as described in our previous communications¹⁻³.

The equations (3) and (4) can be rearranged as

$$\text{p}K_1 = B + \log U_{\text{H}^+}^{\text{O}} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\text{p}K_2 = B' + \log U_{\text{H}^+}^{\text{O}} + \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{\text{OH}^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (6)$$

where, C is the concentration of neutral amino acid, a or b

the concentration of acid or base respectively, and C_{H^+} or C_{OH^-} the concentration of H^+ or OH^- ion in the experimental solution (determined pH-metrically). In aqueous binary mixtures, we actually determine the meter reading (B -values) which with appropriate corrections ($\log U_H$)¹⁻⁴ give H^+ ion concentrations. For the determination of C_{OH^-} , the values of autoprotolysis constants of water in mixed solvents are necessary. The approximate autoprotolysis constants of water in D + H₂O mixtures were determined in this laboratory pH-metrically as suggested by Wooley *et al.*⁷. The autoprotolysis constants of water in mixed solvents were utilised to calculate C_{OH^-} values though considerable uncertainty arises in the accurate determination of autoprotolysis constants at higher percentages of dioxane (above 50 wt% of D).

The highest concentrations of amino acids and HClO₄ or NaOH used are 1.0×10^{-2} and $3.0-7.0 \times 10^{-3}$ respectively. In dilute solutions, the activity coefficients of amino acids have been taken to be unity in the concentration ranges studied in view of lack of data of RH^\pm in aqueous as well as in mixed solvents. This may involve slight error but it is unavoidable. In case of pK_1 , the effect would be only marginal as f_{H^+} and $f_{RH_2^+}$ cancel each other; error arises from uncertain f_{RH^\pm} terms. But considerable uncertainty would arise in case of pK_2 values where the contributions from the term $f_{H^+} f_{R^-} / f_{RH^\pm}$ should be considerable.

The free energies of transfer for the first and second dissociations of amino acids have been calculated in the usual way,

$$\Delta G_t^0(1) = 2.303 RT [pK_s(1) - pK_w(1)] \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Delta G_t^0(2) = 2.303 RT [pK_s(2) - pK_w(2)] \quad (8)$$

The pK_1 and pK_2 values in D + H₂O mixtures are presented in Table 1. Comparison of the values in D + H₂O mixtures are not possible due to lack of data. However, the variation in pK_2 values may be appreciable and the e.m.f. readings in the alkaline solutions are quite unstable similar

to those observed by Edsall and Blanchard⁸. The pK_1 values of all the amino acids increase with increase in dioxane content of the mixture but the magnitude of increase is usually smaller than those of the corresponding carboxylic acids where the lowering of dielectric constant cause decrease in the dissociation of the acid but in case of amino acids, conversion of RH^\pm into ions takes place leading to a decrease in K_1 values. However, the change in the dissociation values in different solvents for different amino acids must be due to change in solute-solvent and hydrophobic interactions of the amino acids.

The pK_1 values were found to be linear functions of $1/\epsilon$ and mole fraction of dioxane at low percentages. Naturally, the deviations arising from changed solute-solvent interactions may be considerable at higher percentages. It is likely that the zwitterionic character changes with the addition of organic co-solvent dioxane (D), and at higher percentages of D, the proportion of zwitterions may decrease. However, the conversion of zwitterion to neutral forms has been found to be very small from the approximate estimate of K_2 values,

$$K_z = \frac{[NH_3^+ RCO_2^-]}{[NH_2 RCO_2 H]} \quad (11)$$

K_z values of glycine, α -alanine and β -alanine, calculated in the way described before^{3,8} using the pK_E values for the reactions, $NH_3^+ RCO_2 Et \rightleftharpoons NH_2 RCO_2 Et + H^+$ from the literature, are given in Table 1. Moreover, the free energy of transfer of amino acids from W \rightarrow D + H₂O mixtures are found to be increasingly unfavourable suggesting that the amino acids are present predominantly as zwitterions even in mixed and non-aqueous solvents^{3,9}. The free energy changes (of dissociation) of amino acids as manifested in $\Delta G_t^0(1)$ and $\Delta G_t^0(2)$ have been found to be predominantly positive (unfavourable) in going from W \rightarrow D + W mixtures. It is apparent that conversion from zwitterion to neutral form has very little effect on ΔG_t^0 values; the main contributory factors are the structural changes of water due to

 TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS (pK_1 AND pK_2) OF AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT DIOXANE + H₂O MIXTURES AT 298 K

Dioxane wt%	$1/\epsilon \cdot 10^2$	L-Valine		L-Asparagine		L-Methionine		L-Threonine		L-Proline		Glycine			α -Alanine			β -Alanine		
		pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$	pK_1	pK_2	$\log K_z$
0.0	1.27	2.32	9.66	2.03	8.80	2.28	9.26	2.15	9.12	1.99	10.60	2.34	9.61	5.39	2.34	9.71	5.46	3.60	10.22	5.53
10.3	1.44	2.44	9.72	2.19	8.98	2.38	9.31	2.29	9.16	2.07	10.64	2.43	9.71	5.30	2.44	9.88	5.36	3.68	10.37	5.45
20.5	1.64	2.60	9.75	2.41	9.04	2.49	9.39	2.43	9.24	2.19	10.68	2.59	9.75	5.14	2.60	9.93	5.20	3.83	10.38	5.30
30.6	1.93	2.78	9.85	2.54	9.17	2.66	9.41	2.57	9.36	2.32	10.78	2.73	9.86	5.00	2.79	10.04	5.01	4.02	10.29	5.11
40.7	2.33	3.02	9.92	2.77	9.23	2.89	9.49	2.86	9.48	2.57	10.82	2.92	9.94	4.81	2.98	10.11	4.82	4.22	10.33	4.91
50.8	2.92	3.28	10.05	3.08	9.40	3.11	9.62	3.03	9.59	2.74	10.90	3.17	10.02	4.56	3.21	10.20	4.59	4.59	10.47	4.54
60.7	3.87	3.52	10.13	3.36	9.51	3.41	9.76	3.26	9.72	2.92	10.94	3.46	10.16	4.27	3.62	10.28	4.18	4.86	10.52	4.27
70.6	5.65	3.48	10.15	3.53	9.62	3.76	9.84	3.71	9.79	3.42	11.01	3.78	10.24	3.95	3.77	10.31	4.03	5.18	10.61	3.95
80.5	9.34	-	-	3.81	9.82	4.21	9.77	4.05	9.75	3.79	10.74	4.28	10.20	3.45	4.39	10.24	3.41	5.67	10.48	3.46

addition of dioxane (with two etheral oxygen atoms), lowering of dielectric constant of the solvent mixtures, changes in the ion-solvent and hydrophobic interactions of the amino acids.

Free energy of transfer of ions can give quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions but can not be determined from these data unless $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$ or $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(2)$ are split into single ion values which is possible using extrathermodynamic assumptions. Thus from equations (1) and (2), we have

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm}) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{or } \Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm}) = -\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm}) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta G_i^{\circ}(R^-) = \Delta G_i^{\circ}(2) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm}) \quad (12)$$

The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm})$ values are taken from our earlier works^{9,10}. The calculated values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^-)$ (from $W \rightarrow D + W$ mixtures) are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FREE ENERGIES OF TRANSFER (kJ mol⁻¹) OF DIFFERENT SPECIES FROM WATER TO DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Dioxane wt%	$-\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$	$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm})$						
		Glycine	α -Alanine	L-Asparagine	L-Methionine	L-Proline	L-Valine	
10.3	1.10	-0.72	-0.89	-1.47	-0.49	-0.48	-1.27	
20.5	1.59	-1.29	-1.88	-2.40	-1.33	-1.08	-1.09	
30.6	2.15	-1.67	-2.71	-2.32	-2.48	-1.78	-1.87	
40.7	2.22	-1.29	-2.04	-3.03	-3.02	-2.31	-2.35	
50.8	2.22	-1.17	-2.68	-2.65	-3.68	-2.81	-3.47	
60.7	1.10	-0.08	-2.25	-1.69	-3.84	-2.54	-2.84	
70.6	-1.22	+4.11	+3.42	+1.50	+0.58	-1.89	-1.64	
80.5	-8.10	+9.55	+7.68	+9.34	+6.66	+3.04	-	
In water : $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm})$		1087.4	1103.7	1102.3	1095.3	1096.8	-1105.3	1099.9
Dioxane wt%	$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(R^-)$	$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(R^-)$						
		Glycine	α -Alanine	L-Asparagine	L-Methionine	L-Proline	L-Valine	
10.3	2.56	2.85	2.67	2.57	2.41	1.96		
20.5	4.12	4.04	4.32	3.79	3.69	4.20		
30.6	6.29	6.04	7.00	4.84	5.43	6.14		
40.7	8.34	8.33	8.08	6.21	6.70	7.57		
50.8	10.35	9.52	11.20	7.54	7.63	8.67		
60.7	11.65	10.50	12.15	7.66	6.91	8.89		
70.6	13.48	12.56	12.20	9.90	6.17	7.39		
80.5	7.79	6.20	9.12	4.38	-2.10	-		
In water : $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(R^-)$		1139.3	1141.3	1141.3	1143.9	1141.3	1143.2	

It is difficult to predict the error range of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^-)$ where errors are compounded from the errors in the determination of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm})$, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$ or, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(2)$ and mainly from $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$. It is to be noted that the errors involved in the determination of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH^{\pm})$, $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$ or $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(2)$

may not be too large but nothing specific can be said about the error range for $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$. The $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$ values determined by us¹⁰ are usually in qualitative agreement with the few values reported by Das and Kundu¹¹ using 'reference electrolyte' method but quantitatively the disagreement is about 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹. The error range in the values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(RH_2^{\pm})$ and $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(R^-)$ must be more than ± 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹. Thus, the fluctuations of single ion values can not be ruled out. The single ion values based on extra-thermodynamic assumptions can never be absolute but in spite of uncertainties, the results can be regarded to be consistent.

It is known that dioxane differs from the alcoholic solvents in its behaviour towards water. Alcohols are usually structure-formers whereas dioxane is a net structure-breaker¹⁰. In spite of the differences of dioxane from other co-solvents, the variation of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{ion})$ (cation or anion) with solvent composition follows the pattern found in water + alcohol and water + ethylene glycol mixtures^{2,3}. The results are consistent with the observation that $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(W \rightarrow D + W)$ of cations and anions are usually negative and positive respectively at low percentages^{2,3} (~50 wt%) but the values tend to reverse at higher percentages. The stabilisation of cations as well as anions are dependent on the acid-base properties of the solvents, Born-type interactions (dependent on radius), polarisability of ions and hydrophobic characters of the groups (particularly at low percentages of D). D + H₂O mixtures have been found to be more basic than water and the basicity has been found to be maximum in the region 45–50 wt%¹⁰ or D. ΔG_i° of ions are very much dependent of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(H^+)$ and therefore, the possibility of reversal of ΔG_i° of ions is quite apparent at higher percentages of D. The changes are not surprising in view of the fact that the proteins and biomolecules change their structure and properties in different solvents and naturally the amino acids show changed behaviour.

From the results, it is apparent that the amino acids in aqueous solution is probably present as an equilibrium mixtures of zwitterions and a very small amount of ions depending on the pH of the solution according to the scheme.

The increase in basicity with addition of D should make the formation of anions rather than cations favourable. However, the observations are exactly opposite. Naturally other factors rather than basicity is of importance. Amino acids are characterised by the presence of hydrophobic and

hydrophilic centres leading to different types of solvation. Both hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions¹² compete for water structure organisation though the nature may be different. The addition of D causes the change in hydrophobic interactions and specific solvation effects in the opposite direction. The hydrophobic interactions are maximum at very low percentages of D and increase with the size of the R group in amino acids. But structure-breaking (of water) effect of D is probably more important. However, the variation of solubility of RH^\pm in D + H₂O mixtures may cause the variation of $\Delta G_t^\circ(RH_2^+)$ and $\Delta G_t^\circ(R^-)$ ions. Though the variations of $\Delta G_t^\circ(RH_2^+)$ and $\Delta G_t^\circ(R^-)$ with solvent composition give quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions, still the solvational aspects are relatively little understood. Further informations may be obtained if it is possible to analyse the $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{ion})$ values in the following way using the scaled particle theory¹³ in spite of limitations as there is no other satisfactory method to know the interaction energies.

The free energy of solvation of an ion (in terms of molarity) can be written as

$$\Delta G_{\text{ion(molar)}}^\circ = \Delta G_{\text{cav(molar)}}^\circ + \Delta G_{\text{int}}^\circ + \Delta G_{\text{(cl)}}^\circ + RT \ln RT/V \quad (13)$$

where, $\Delta G_{\text{cav}}^\circ$ is the free energy change to create a cavity to accommodate the solute in the solvent, $\Delta G_{\text{int}}^\circ$ the free energy of interaction between solute and solvent, V the molar volume of the solvent in question; $\Delta G_{\text{cl}}^\circ$ explained later. $\Delta G_{\text{cav}}^\circ$ has been calculated in the way described by Kim¹⁴ and given in details in a previous communication¹⁵. The radii of some of the amino acids have been obtained from literature¹⁶.

The application of the 'scaled particle' theory has the obvious drawback that the amino acids can not be treated as hard sphere molecules and there are also uncertainties regarding the radii of unsymmetrical acids. But the errors may be expected to be minimised in the calculation of $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav)}}^\circ$ [$W \rightarrow D + W$ mixtures] so that $\Delta G_{\text{t(ion)}}^\circ$ can be represented as

$$\Delta G_{\text{t(ion)}}^\circ = \Delta G_{\text{t(cav)molar}}^\circ + \Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ + \Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ + RT \ln V_s/V_w \quad (14)$$

The $\Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ$ values have been calculated using Born equation¹⁷ assuming spherical disposition of amino acids in solution. However, the uncertainties regarding the radii of cations and anions (may be slightly different) of the unsymmetrical amino acids can not be avoided. The $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (RH_2^+) and $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (R^-) [$W \rightarrow D + W$] for a few amino acids are presented in Table 3. The $\Delta G_{\text{cav}}^\circ$, $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav)}}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ$ are recorded in Table 4. The results indicate, $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (RH_2^+) [$W \rightarrow D + W$] is increasingly favourable for glycine, alanine (upto 60 wt% of D) but unfavourable for L-asparagine

TABLE 3— $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (RH_2^+) AND $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (R^-) VALUES OF AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Dioxane vol %	Glycine	α -Alanine	L-Asparagine	L-Methionine
$\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (RH_2^+):				
10	-0.55	-0.37	-0.63	0.90
20	-0.99	-0.83	-0.64	1.56
30	-1.29	-1.08	+0.47	2.18
40	-1.29	-0.30	+0.31	2.92
50	-1.88	-0.98	+0.10	3.70
60	-3.16	-1.44	+2.01	4.41
70	-2.25	+1.42	+3.33	8.36
80	-4.17	+0.75	+8.29	14.56
$\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (R^-):				
10	2.73	3.37	3.60	3.96
20	4.42	5.09	6.08	6.68
30	6.67	7.67	9.79	9.50
40	8.34	10.07	11.42	12.15
50	9.64	11.22	13.95	14.92
60	9.25	11.31	15.85	15.91
70	7.12	10.56	14.03	17.68
80	-5.93	-0.73	8.07	12.28

TABLE 4— $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav(molar))}}^\circ$ (1) VALUES, $\Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ$ (2) BORN VALUES OF DIFFERENT AMINO ACIDS IN DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K

Dioxane vol%	Glycine		α -Alanine		L-Asparagine		L-Methionine	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
0	44.31		59.82		74.62		98.83	
10	43.63	0.48	58.84	0.43	73.56	0.40	97.07	0.35
20	42.91	1.10	57.78	0.99	71.95	0.92	95.13	0.82
30	41.99	1.49	56.45	1.74	70.23	1.61	92.74	1.44
40	41.19	3.12	55.28	2.80	68.70	2.59	90.58	2.32
50	40.14	4.88	54.75	4.37	67.84	4.04	87.83	3.63
60	39.01	7.70	52.11	6.90	64.56	6.37	84.85	5.74
70	37.69	12.98	50.18	11.64	62.06	10.74	81.38	9.68
80	34.10	23.93	45.29	21.46	55.89	19.79	73.11	17.83
90	34.33		45.36		55.45		72.57	
100	31.93		41.82		51.16		66.29	

(above 20 wt%) and methionine, whereas $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ (R^-) is always unfavourable. The differences in the interaction energies arise from increasingly negative $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav)}}^\circ$ values in going from [$W \rightarrow D + W$] mixtures. The sequence of $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav)}}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ$ is : glycine > alanine > asparagine > methionine. Since these amino acids are formed by the replacement of H-atoms of glycine by CH₃ (alanine), CONH₂ (asparagine), CH₂-S-CH₃ (methionine) naturally difference in $\Delta G_{\text{t(int)}}^\circ$ terms of any amino acid and glycine with proper corrections for $\Delta G_{\text{t(cav)}}^\circ$ and $\Delta G_{\text{t(el)}}^\circ$ gives the change in the interaction energies of cations and anions due to the introduction of different groups in glycine. Even [$\Delta G_{\text{t(ion)amino acid}}^\circ - \Delta G_{\text{t(ion)glycine}}^\circ$], a purely experimen-

tal quantity represents the change in the interaction energies due to substitution though proper corrections for volume effect (cavity and electrostatic effect) are imperative to know the change in interaction energies.

In absence of any suitable model for calculation of interaction energies, the method presented in this communication can be regarded to be fairly accurate in predicting the interaction energies in spite of limitations.

Experimental

The amino acids utilised in the present study are of highest purity available from Sigma, E. Merck, B.D.H. and Loba-chemie. The amino acids (except for guaranteed qualities) were purified by crystallisation from ethanol + water mixtures. The amino acids were estimated titrimetrically in the usual way using acid-free formaldehyde solution. Dioxane was purified as described earlier^{10,18}.

The H⁺ ion concentrations in mixed solvents were determined as described before^{1-3,18,19}. Other experimental details are similar to those described in our earlier communications¹⁻³. For the determination of acid dissociation constants of dipolar ions, the meter readings of a number of solutions of HClO₄ of varying concentrations (3-7 × 10⁻³ M) were measured in presence and absence of a definite concentration of amino acids. The process was the same for each of the amino acids. The differences of H⁺ ion concentrations obtained from the meter readings of the corresponding solutions give the amount of LH⁺ and the meter readings give the [H⁺] ion concentration of the solution. For the determination of the second dissociation constants of amino acids, the process was same, only HClO₄ being replaced by NaOH.

pH was determined at 298 K using a Krick, Labor pH-meter with a combined Ag/AgCl electrode (Ingold Elektroden).

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References

1. A. K. CHATTOPADHYAY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1977, **15A**, 930.
2. B. P. DEY, S. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1982, **21**, 886; A. PAL, B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1986, **25**, 322; S. K. CHAKRABORTY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 399; B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI *Indian J Chem Sect A* 1986, **25**, 136.
3. S. C. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1995 **72**.
4. J. P. GREENSTEIN and M. WINITZ, "Chemistry of the Amino Acids", Wiley, New York 1961, Vol. I, Chap. 2.
5. R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1973, Chap. 8.
6. A. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1980 **57**, 971.
7. E. M. WOOLLEY, D. G. HURKOT and L. G. HEPLER, *J Phys Chem* 1970, **74**, 3908 E. M. WOOLLEY and L. G. HEPLER, *Anal Chem* 1972, **44**, 1520.
8. J. J. EDSALL and BLANCHARD, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1933 **25**, 2337
9. K. MAJUMDAR (SENGUPTA), K. K. MAJUMDAR and S. C. LAHIRI communicated
10. K. MAJUMDAR (SENGUPTA), S. C. LAHIRI and D. C. MUKHERJEE *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 365.
11. A. K. DAS and K. K. KUNDU, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1978 **16** 467.
12. J. P. MORE, J. FAUVE, L. AVEDIKIAR and J. JUILLARD *J Soln Chem.*, 1974 **3**, 403; N. DOLLET and J. JUILLARD, *J Soln Chem* 1976, **5**, 77; Y. POINUD and J. JUILLARD, *J Chem Soc, Faraday Trans. 1*, 1977 **73**, 1907
13. R. A. PIEROTTI, *J Phys Chem*, 1965, **69**, 281; *Chem Rev* 1976 **76**, 717.
14. J. KIM, *Z Phys Chem (N F)*, 1978, **113**, 129.
15. S. DUTTA, A. K. MONDAI, B. P. DEY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 753.
16. F. SHAHIDI and P. G. FARRELL, *J Chem Soc, Faraday Trans. 1* 1981, **77**, 963.
17. M. BORN, *Z Physik*, 1920 **1**, 45.
18. S. K. PAL, U. C. BHATTACHARYYA, S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 497.
19. L. G. VANUITERT and C. C. HAAS, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1953, **75** 451; U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z Phys Chem (N F)*, 1966, **50**, 1083.